

Brianne Diminia Crowell

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As a mission-driven Change Agent with a fervent dedication to making a positive impact, I bring over a decade of extensive experience in education and writing services. Throughout my career, I have been recognized for fostering accelerated growth with sustainable top-tier successes.

Skills: My expertise spans various domains, including English Language Arts, Curriculum Development, Writing Services, Business Administration, Behavioral Health, Staff Motivation and Training, as well as Reporting & Documentation. I possess outstanding verbal and written communication, presentation, and listening skills.

Education: I earned a Masters in Educational Leadership from Clark Atlanta University in 2021, complemented by a Bachelor of Arts (B.A) in English from Drew University in 2017.

Career Snapshot: In my roles, I have demonstrated exceptional leadership skills, strategic thinking, and an intuitive, empathetic approach to management. I am adept at initiating positive change, improving procedures and processes within teams, and fostering an inspiring culture through vision, empowerment, and development. My strong academic acumen is complemented by excellent problem-solving, team-building, and client relationship management skills.

Professional Experience:

Jersey City Board of Education (Current Position) As a 5th-grade English Arts Teacher, I develop and maintain individualized lesson plans, supervise educational activities, and ensure high academic standards in compliance with policies.

College Essay Writing Coach (Remote) In this role, I provided one-on-one coaching sessions to high school students, offering constructive feedback on content, structure, grammar, and overall writing style. I also conducted group workshops and created engaging presentations to assist students in developing effective writing techniques.

ClubX Youthniversity's Xposure Foundation Inc/Tutor Me Education As a part of the Assessment and Skillbuilding Team/Virtual English Tutor, I developed and implemented virtual lesson plans, improving student performance in English grammar, comprehension, writing composition, and test prep for students with diverse needs.

Clark Atlanta University – Behavioral Health Program As an HBCU C.A.R.E.S. Graduate Assistant, I provided academic support and counseling, contributing to a 10% increase in racial and ethnic minority students within a year. I also drove program awareness through various informative web content and organized training sessions.

Online Learning and Continuing Education As an Expert Data Consultant, I served as a subject matter expert on content data review analysis, collaborating with stakeholders to enhance student success. I actively participated in planning and organizing Professional Development Workshops for university staff members.

Study Abroad to South Africa, Jersey City, NJ In the role of Study Abroad Consultant, I recruited and screened undergraduate students, maintained positive relationships with study abroad advisors, and consistently achieved organizational objectives.

Acorn Academy, Madison, NJ As an Early Childhood Teacher Assistant, I provided crucial support to lead teachers, reinforcing lessons, tutoring students, documenting progress, and overseeing classroom behavior.

In summary, I am a self-motivated professional with a proven ability to grasp new concepts quickly in an ambiguous environment. Proficient in computer applications, including Microsoft Office products, I bring a unique blend of academic expertise, leadership skills, and a passion for positive change to every role I undertake.